

Report of the Bologna Meeting on Open Research Information

May 28 2025, University of Bologna

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Meeting highlights

From Paris to Bologna: Advancing the Barcelona Declaration Collectively

On May 28th 2025, signatories, supporters, and other interested participants gathered in Bologna for a day dedicated to advancing the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information. The meeting took place in the context of the [5th Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata \(WOOC2025\)](#), co-organized by the Barcelona Declaration, the University of Bologna and OpenCitations.

The event brought together key stakeholders to reflect on the implementation of the Declaration and continue shaping its future. Designed in a workshop-like format, the day focused on advancing the [actions outlined in the roadmap](#) collectively developed at the [Paris Conference on Open Research Information](#). The day also offered an opportunity for the [Barcelona Declaration working groups](#) to present their activities and plans, and discuss them with a broader audience. Opening up the Barcelona Declaration “kitchen” to other interested participants reflected a strong commitment to transparency and collaborative progress.

The day was launched with opening remarks by Raffaella Campaner, Vice Rector for International Relations at the University of Bologna, and Bianca Kramer, Executive Director of the Barcelona Declaration, who presented Barcelona Declaration: Introduction & Where are we now?. Their contributions set the stage for an engaging and action-oriented day.

To ground the discussions in practical experience, three signatories representing different institutional contexts and geographies shared short presentations: Carla Carbonell Cortés from *Fundación “la Caixa”*, John Chodacki from the *California Digital Library*, and Ana Ranitovic from University of Groningen, in her capacity as chair of the working group of *Dutch signatories of the Barcelona Declaration*. Each reflected on how the Declaration is being implemented in their specific setting, illustrating its adaptability.

The second part of the day focused on collaborative work and next steps for the Barcelona Declaration. In two rounds of breakout sessions, six [working groups](#) shared updates, priorities, and early ideas with participants in an open and collaborative setting. These sessions were followed by plenary recaps, where coordinators reported back on the discussions and gathered feedback to inform the ongoing development of the roadmap.

Thanks to its hybrid format, and in line with the Barcelona Declaration’s ongoing efforts to ensure inclusive participation and sustained community engagement, almost 200 participants from 35 countries took part in the discussions. This diversity of perspectives nurtured a strong sense of collective purpose and sparked rich conversations about how change can be driven collaboratively.

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Full Report

Opening Reflections and Strategic Foundations of the Barcelona Declaration

The day began with opening remarks from Raffaella Campaner, Vice Rector for International Relations at the University of Bologna. She emphasized the importance of joint and collective action, stressing that “these are not abstract ideals but urgent prompts for real change in how scientific knowledge is produced, shared, and managed.” Raffaella also highlighted the University of Bologna’s strong commitment to the principles of the Barcelona Declaration, spanning knowledge production, data sharing, infrastructure management, and resource allocation.

Next, Bianca Kramer, Executive Director of the Barcelona Declaration, took a moment to describe the [existing organization of the Barcelona Declaration](#), introducing the current steering group members, her own role, and Bárbara Rivera López as Community Manager.

In her presentation, *Barcelona Declaration: Introduction & Where are we now*, Bianca invited the audience to reflect on key questions around access, ownership, and control of research information, prompting participants to consider where research outputs are located, who can access them, and how they are evaluated. These reflections, she noted, are increasingly relevant in discussions around academic and digital sovereignty. For institutions, they offer a reason to step back and think strategically: How are we managing our research information? And are we ensuring it is accessible, inclusive, and under the control of the academic community itself? These reflections laid the groundwork for Bianca’s introduction of the Barcelona Declaration and helped set the stage for a deeper look into its goals and progress.

Building on this, she explained how the Declaration primarily targets organizations that carry out, fund, and evaluate research, such as universities, research institutions, and governments, while also actively involving key infrastructure providers: the people and organizations who build and maintain the services that make open research information possible. Achieving the kind of change envisioned by the Declaration requires the combined efforts of all these actors.

From Principles to Practice: Signatories’ Journeys in Implementing the Barcelona Declaration

To ground these ideas in practice, the next part of the program featured short presentations from three diverse signatories of the Barcelona Declaration. Each represented a different type of institution and national context and shared how the Declaration is being implemented in their settings.

The first presentation offered the perspective of a research funder. Carla Carbonell Cortés, Associate General Director of Research and Fellowships at “la Caixa” Foundation, joined the meeting online to share why the Declaration resonates with one of the world’s largest private foundations. She presented the strategic rationale behind the foundation’s decision to sign the Barcelona Declaration, highlighting the importance of improving the contextualization of funding metadata, to optimize bibliographic metadata use, supporting inclusive and robust evaluation practices, and reinforcing institutional leadership through alignment with international best practices.

Carla also shared that the principles of the Declaration are already informing their approach to procurement and negotiations. Joining the Barcelona Declaration (and also the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment - CoARA) has helped them move forward in these areas. In line with the principles of the Barcelona Declaration, she highlighted a key change in their Health Research Call, where traditional CVs have been replaced with more targeted applicant information and where reviewers are encouraged to focus on content over metrics. “A major step toward fairer and more meaningful evaluation,” she noted.

The second presentation offered the perspective of a major university-based digital library with a strong role in infrastructure. John Chodacki, representing the California Digital Library (CDL), reflected on how the Declaration supports institutional alignment and drives change across a complex academic system. As he explained, signing the Barcelona Declaration felt like a natural (if slightly overdue) step. “The real question is not why we signed the Barcelona Declaration, but rather why we have not done it earlier,” he noted. CDL was the [first university-based organization in the United States to sign the Declaration](#).

As part of the signing process, CDL published an [internal assessment](#) of how it is currently managing research information across its services. This resource was shared to support other institutions considering similar steps toward aligning with the commitments of the Barcelona Declaration.

For the University of California system, the Declaration represents a strategic opportunity to further align internal processes and inform both practices and policies. Advancing this direction of work, CDL is co-leading [COMET](#), a collaborative initiative focused on improving metadata quality and interoperability. For CDL, this is a clear example of how the Declaration can catalyze not only institutional change, but also broader community action in open scholarship.

The final presentation brought in a national and institutional perspective. Ana Ranitovic, speaking from her experience at the University of Groningen and on behalf of the Dutch signatories of the Barcelona Declaration, discussed the challenges of moving from commitment to implementation. While signing the Declaration aligned naturally with her university’s Open Science strategy, Ana noted that putting it into practice required fundamental changes to core institutional processes, from research assessment and output management to negotiation systems and tracking tools.

Building on their shared commitment, the national network of Dutch signatories focused on practical collaboration: discussing motivations, identifying shared challenges, and exploring opportunities for joint action. This has included rethinking quality assurance based on openness and looking into open alternatives to commercial systems. “These topics are not unique to the Netherlands, which speaks to the global relevance of the Declaration’s aims” Ana added.

She also highlighted the benefits of peer learning, with institutions drawing insights from each other’s pilots and adapting existing solutions: a dynamic that has directly benefited Groningen. Beyond these practical gains, the network is contributing to a broader culture shift and has begun sharing recommendations for forming similar national-level collaborations.

From the Barcelona Declaration “Kitchen”: Recipes for Change in the Making

The second part of the day took on a workshop-like character, centred on the actions outlined in the roadmap collectively developed during the [Paris Conference on Open Research Information](#).

This was an opportunity not only to explore next steps, but also to see the Barcelona Declaration community in action. Over two rounds of parallel breakout sessions, six [working groups](#) met to present their plans, discuss priorities, and engage with other participants in a hybrid format.

Following the breakout sessions, participants reconvened for two plenary recaps, each featuring three working groups. These provided a space for working group coordinators to report back on the discussions held during their breakout sessions, highlighting key takeaways, feedback received, and ideas for next steps. Reports were kept short and focused to allow time for open discussion, both in the room and online.

By opening up the “kitchen” of the Barcelona Declaration, this sharing of early ideas, challenges, and coordination efforts, the process aimed to foster transparency and invite meaningful collaboration between signatories, supporters, and the broader community.

Most working groups are organised into one or more taskforces that focus on specific objectives and areas of implementation. The summaries below present key developments, ongoing priorities, and areas of emerging interest across the six working groups. They reflect the community’s collaborative efforts to advance the Declaration’s principles through concrete actions, and offer a snapshot of both progress made and the directions being explored.

Working Group 1 - Journal Article and Book Metadata

Working group coordinators: Ludo Waltman (Leiden University), Judith Naidorf, Mariangela Napoli (Consejo Latinoamericano de Ciencias Sociales - CLACSO-Universidad de Buenos Aires)
Additional taskforce coordinators: Adam Buttrick (CDL), Dominic Mitchell (DOAJ)

This working group aims to ensure that key metadata are made openly available by publishers. To support this goal, a framework describing essential metadata elements is being developed. It also contributes to publisher negotiations and explores affordable paths for under-resourced communities.

Taskforce 1 - Framework and Principles

This taskforce focuses on developing a framework to define key metadata elements that publishers should provide. At the Bologna meeting, participants engaged in a prioritization exercise, where they provided feedback on the perceived value and complexity involved in producing the fields listed in [Crossref's Participation Reports](#). This exercise contained two components: a quantitative ranking of both aspects for each field (value and effort to produce), followed by a group discussion of why participants ranked these values as such to capture their more qualitative concerns.

The outcomes of this session will help shape an initial understanding of Barcelona Declaration signatories' priorities and perceived barriers with the provisioning of these metadata elements, and will also inform a broader, more structured data-gathering process.

Taskforce 2 - Publisher Negotiations

This taskforce is working on incorporating openness of publication metadata in negotiations with publishers, and potentially also with other service providers. The initial focus is on teaming up with library consortia committed to advancing openness of publication metadata. The [OA2020 initiative](#) has already expressed an interest to work together with the Barcelona Declaration and engage its network of library consortia.

Taskforce 3 - Poorly-Resourced Publishers

This taskforce focuses on the needs of poorly-resourced publishers within the research information ecosystem. Its work is guided by two main objectives: developing a list of required and desirable metadata elements, and producing a set of best practices for recognizing and overcoming pain points in metadata collection and dissemination. Work on the first objective began during the Bologna meeting with a polling exercise involving participants.

As the taskforce moves forward, it will consider additional factors such as how and when metadata is shared with open infrastructures, the impact of persistent identifiers (PIDs), the importance of multilingualism, interoperability of open usage data, and the availability of supporting tools.

Addressing Global Diversity in Scholarly Publishing Practices

As the taskforces in Working Group 1 move forward with their respective focuses (metadata frameworks, publisher negotiations, and support for under-resourced publishers), it is essential to consider the diversity of scholarly publishing models across regions.

Publishing practices in, for instance, Latin America are quite different from those in Europe and North America. In particular, many publishers in Latin America are non-commercial, as most of them are established and financially supported by universities, mainly public. As a result, Latin America is the region with the largest number of non-commercial Diamond open access journals worldwide.

Working Group 1 is committed to developing dedicated strategies for addressing the unique characteristics of scholarly publishing in different geographical regions. We aim to work closely together with publishing infrastructure providers. As an example, the Open Journal System (OJS) infrastructure provided by the Public Knowledge Project (PKP), a supporter of the Barcelona Declaration, serves as the backbone for many publishers in Latin America. We intend to work closely together with infrastructure providers such as PKP to address the specific infrastructure challenges faced by publishers in Latin America and other regions.

These cross-regional perspectives will inform the implementation of the group's work, helping ensure that proposed solutions are inclusive, adaptable, and globally relevant.

Working Group 2 - Metadata for Research Outputs in Repositories

Working group coordinator: Bianca Kramer (Barcelona Declaration) - interim

This working group focuses on metadata for research outputs in institutional repositories, preprint repositories and data repositories - with the aim of expanding the set of research output types for which high quality metadata is available, and ensuring that this growth contributes to the expansion of open research information systems.

Taskforce 1 - Metadata in Institutional Repositories

This taskforce focuses on the importance of good quality metadata in institutional repositories, balanced with the effort it takes to achieve that. At the Bologna meeting, participants discussed the extent to which repository workflows still depend heavily on manual labor, and explored how existing metadata schemas and more automated processes could help reduce that workload. The conversation also emphasized the need for institutional recognition and support for the work involved in running institutional repositories. Additionally, participants reflected on how existing options for curation of affiliation data in external databases (such as provided for OpenAlex and OpenAIRE) can help institutions improve their metadata and make it more usable.

The flows of research information across repositories, metadata aggregators, and bibliographic databases reflect the complex interdependencies within the scholarly ecosystem. Ensuring that these exchanges are well supported through better-aligned workflows can enhance metadata quality and help reduce workloads across institutions.

Taskforce 2 - Machine-learning pipelines

This taskforce is concerned with existing and future implementation of machine-learning pipelines to detect datasets and software from full-text. The plans of the taskforce include organizing a meeting to bring together existing initiatives in this space, and explore how they contribute to open research information, as well as how they relate to the Barcelona Declaration commitments.

A third priority of the working group is to draft guidelines to create and use linked research objects, identifying strategies, tools and actions to capture and leverage metadata for research outputs other than articles. No group has been formed around this taskforce yet.

Working Group 3 - Funding Metadata

Working group coordinators: Hans de Jonge (Dutch Research Council - NWO), Katharina Rieck (Austrian Science Fund - FWF), Zoé Ancion (Agence Nationale de la Recherche - ANR)

This working group aims to improve funding metadata availability through a workshop with key stakeholders and the development of advocacy resources on grant metadata practices.

Taskforce 1 - Funding metadata workshop

This taskforce focuses on organizing a workshop with publishers and manuscript submission system vendors to explore concrete actions for improving the availability of funding metadata in Crossref. During the Bologna meeting, examples were shared of how funders that have signed the Barcelona Declaration are working to implement the Declaration's four commitments, which includes making more funding information available. At the session, insights from a previous workshop with publishers were revisited, highlighting the central role of submission systems in correctly capturing, retaining, and depositing funding metadata to Crossref. An interactive exercise invited participants to reflect on two key questions: (i) why is having open funding data important / who benefits?; and (ii) what mechanisms do we have to improve the current situation with some publishers submitting very complete and comprehensive funding data and many not depositing any.

The input gathered will inform the design and focus of the upcoming workshop.

Taskforce 2 - Practical Resources on Grant Metadata Sharing by Funders

This taskforce focuses on the production and dissemination of resources to support funders in the implementation of grant identifiers. During the Bologna meeting, discussions confirmed strong interest from the community in the wider adoption of grant IDs, while also highlighting concerns about the currently limited uptake among funders. Participants called on DOI registration agencies to simplify the implementation process for Grant DOIs.

The taskforce will hold its first brainstorming session before the summer, with the aim of identifying the most useful types of resources (both technical, such as XML examples, and advocacy-oriented) to support funders in implementing Grant DOIs, lowering barriers to adoption, and encouraging the sharing of richer metadata specific to grant funding.

Working Group 4 - Replacing Closed Systems for Research Information

Coordinators: Amélie Church (Sorbonne Université) and Ignasi Labastida (Universitat de Barcelona)

This working group explores pathways for adopting open research information systems, including coordination around moving away from closed infrastructures. It also addresses capacity building and training needs within institutions. Planned actions include a survey aimed at analysing the current landscape—identifying which systems are being used, for what purposes, how they could be substituted by open alternatives, and the extent to which open systems are already being adopted. The survey will also help define the types of training needed to effectively support the use of open systems.

During the Bologna meeting, the group discussed the scope and target audience of the planned survey. There was consensus that it should be directed primarily to signatories of the Declaration rather than a broader audience. Participants highlighted the importance of including diverse institutional stakeholders and reflected on potential challenges in the implementation process. The idea of complementing the survey with focus groups was also raised, as a way to capture more in-depth and qualitative insights.

Looking ahead, the group plans to collect concrete use cases from institutions that have removed closed systems and are now using open research information resources. Focus groups will also be organized to capture diverse institutional perspectives on this transition. In parallel, the group will perform a literature review to gather insights comparing open and closed research information systems.

To support broader engagement, the working group also plans to host a webinar this fall to spark a discussion around institutional transitions to open research information systems. The session will build on the example of Sorbonne University, while inviting other institutions to share their experiences and challenges in moving away from closed systems.

Working Group 5 - Sustaining Infrastructures

Working group coordinator: to be determined

This working group focuses on the sustainability of the infrastructures that enable open research information. Advancing in this space requires ensuring lasting support for the infrastructures that underpin them. This has long been a challenge— trying to bridge the interests of infrastructures requiring resources and the perspectives of those expected to fund them. It is also a topic already addressed by other initiatives such as [SCOSS](#), [Invest in Open Infrastructure](#), and more recently, [TSOSI](#).

This working group was presented in a plenary session at the Bologna meeting, during which several potential areas of focus were outlined.

Proposed actions include identifying common ground between institutions and open research infrastructures (e.g. around funding needs and mechanisms for open research infrastructures, motives that lead funders to invest in open science infrastructure, and funding stream analysis), and developing a sustainability checklist that reflects the expectations of key stakeholders. Other ideas involve mapping existing infrastructures and their interconnections, creating adaptable guidelines for sustainable strategies, and compiling resources to support advocacy for open research infrastructures.

Looking ahead, the Barcelona Declaration will carefully consider how this working group can add value without duplicating existing initiatives. Rather than replicating what others are already doing, the working group seeks to explore how current efforts can be mobilized and extended to better support signatory organizations in sustaining the open infrastructures that underpin research information. Strong leadership from academic institutions will be essential in turning this into a shared and actionable agenda.

Working Group 6 - Evaluating Open Research Information Sources

Working group coordinator: Stefano Bolelli Gallevi (Università degli Studi di Milano)

This working group focuses on the evaluation of open research information sources to inform and support their adoption by institutions. Initially called ‘Evaluating open data’, a name change was proposed to better reflect the working group’s scope and to avoid confusion between research data and research information (metadata).

During the breakout session in Bologna, participants voted to adopt the new title “Evaluating open research information sources”. The group also presented the background definition it had developed on open research information sources to help guide its work:

Open research information sources are digital platforms using open standards for collecting, preserving, sharing, and enabling the reuse of all kind of metadata related to scientific research, including those on actors (e.g. persons, organizations), their roles (e.g. authors, affiliations, funders, publishers), and activities (e.g., projects, funding), outputs (e.g. publications, research data, software, samples, experiments) and properties (e.g. identifiers, venues, scientific fields and subjects), as well as relations between them and metrics on them (e.g. citations, altmetrics).

They are committed to openness, aiming to reduce legal, technical and social barriers to use and reuse of research information.

Examples are bibliographic databases, software archives, data repositories, current research information systems, PID registries, metrics and metadata registries, irrespective of their size.

The next steps for this working group include developing a set of criteria for the evaluation of open research information sources. In the breakout session, potential criteria relevant for their adoption were presented and discussed. These include open metadata, standardized protocols, open source software, the source being free to access and free of restrictions, use of persistent identifiers, use of open licenses, transparency of processing, transparency of provenance. Additional criteria around coverage, completeness, quality, governance and business model were also discussed.

Longer term actions are to develop a set of reporting guidelines for evaluations, create an overview of projects for developing evaluation tools and methods, and to support and implement them in a monitoring framework.

Working Group 7 - Evidence of Benefits of Open Research Information

Working group coordinators: Núria Benítez Monforte (Institució CERCA) and Christian Hauschke (TIB - Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology)

This working group focuses on clarifying the benefits of open research information for researchers and institutional leadership and management. It plans to collect case studies from signatories and develop a stakeholder map and taxonomy of benefits.

Taskforce 1 - Case Studies

This taskforce focuses on collecting and showcasing compelling use cases that demonstrate the benefits of open research information. The participants met online during the Bologna event, where a proposal for a survey was discussed and its focus refined. Rather than concentrating on technical details, participants emphasized the importance of narrative-driven contributions. It was also agreed that different formats (such as written accounts, audio, or video) should be welcomed.

Looking ahead, it was suggested that the initiative should not rely on a one-off survey but instead create a permanent mechanism for collecting and curating case studies. Conversations about this ongoing setup have already started with other working group coordinators and will continue in the upcoming taskforce meetings.

Taskforce 2 - Stakeholder Map / Taxonomy of Benefits

This taskforce focuses on developing a taxonomy of benefits and stakeholders, and mapping the relationships between them. During the in-person meeting in Bologna, it became clear that the taskforce would benefit from broader perspectives. Participants proposed several directions to enhance the work: using standardized stakeholder vocabularies; improving how benefits are described; recognizing that benefits may differ depending on the stakeholder; and exploring whether narrative-driven stories could serve the purpose more effectively than a traditional stakeholder map.

As a next step, this taskforce will explore these proposed directions further and identify the most suitable approach to develop a useful and adaptable stakeholder framework.

Shaping the Future of the Barcelona Declaration: Governance, Collaboration, and Global Reach

The day concluded with a forward-looking session led by Cameron Neylon (Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative and member of the Barcelona Declaration Steering Group), Ludo Waltman (Centre for Science and Technology Studies, Leiden University and member of the Barcelona Declaration Steering Group) and Bianca Kramer (Executive Director of the Barcelona Declaration). Together, they outlined the areas of work now emerging as priorities for the next steps of the Barcelona Declaration.

A key area currently under discussion is the transition toward a more permanent governance structure, with a representative Governing Board expected to be in place by the end of the year. This board will be responsible for setting strategic priorities, guiding the Declaration's formal positions, and ensuring inclusive, representative oversight, without being involved in day-to-day management. Efforts are underway to explore broader representation in the board's composition, including different types of organizations and geographical diversity.

During the meeting, participants' input was invited on how governance of the Declaration could or should evolve. A variety of perspectives was offered, including the suggestion that the current Steering Group structure may suffice and there may be no need for new governance structures. John Chodacki, representing the California Digital Library (CDL), emphasized that "we're here because we trust the people currently leading this work."

Looking ahead, the Barcelona Declaration will also seek to deepen collaboration with aligned initiatives. This may include the formation of joint task forces, coordinated working group activities, and shared efforts at the national level, where change often happens more rapidly and with stronger local engagement.

A continued emphasis on global inclusivity was also highlighted. This includes improving language accessibility and finding new ways to support participation from underrepresented communities. Regional events, multilingual resources, and context-specific support will be explored as part of this effort.

Looking ahead, a next meeting for Barcelona Declaration signatories and supporters is envisioned for the second half of 2026. The aim is to create a space for shared reflection and coordination, with a particular focus on engaging participants at policy and decision-making levels. The intention is for the meeting to be co-organized with one or more signatory organizations and to take into account opportunities for global representation as well as overall carbon footprint.

As the day came to a close, there was a strong sense that the ideas seeded last year in Paris, and shaped through collective action since, are now taking root. The Barcelona Declaration is evolving as an initiative that drives change at technical, operational, and strategic levels. It enables ongoing collaboration through its network of working groups and expands its reach and impact through targeted dissemination and outreach activities. The transition to open research information is moving full steam ahead!